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SMART MAN HOLE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, most people live in metropolitan areas, regardless of the nation. Through the analysis of real-time and historical data, the management of urban infrastructure systems is improved as a consequence of a better knowledge of these systems. It is predicted to increase even more by 2030. Underground drainage is crucial to ensuring a safe, hygienic environment and enough sanitation for densely populated metropolitan areas, since these places are turning to smart techniques via the Internet of Things or by redesigning the current service sector. A robust subterranean drainage system is required for this. By making the current system simpler and less expensive to maintain, we can effect change. This may be achieved by significantly cutting down on the time needed to identify the afflicted region. Real-time data, such as the water flow rate and the quantity of harmful gasses, may be obtained by installing sensor-based manhole covers at crucial areas instead of the current ones. By sending this data to the approved service station before it is blocked, a prompt repair schedule may be implemented, avoiding street flooding.

Keywords: data center, manhole, flow rate, sensor, and power independence.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is a ground-breaking program that aims to transform the management of urban infrastructure. Manhole covers are essential parts of utility networks in urban settings because they guarantee that utility and sewage lines operate correctly. But these coverings are vulnerable to a number of problems, including

as theft, relocation, and deterioration, all of which may pose serious dangers to public safety and cause interruptions to vital services. In an unyielding effort to solve these problems, this project introduces a complete and real-time monitoring system for manhole covers using cutting-edge technology. The initiative's major goals are varied and include improving infrastructure maintenance procedures, preventing unwanted access, increasing public safety, analyzing data in real time, and managing infrastructure costs effectively.

Figure .1: Manhole Monitoring

The safety enhancement aspect of the project is pivotal, aiming to promptly identify and rectify issues related to manhole covers such as open, displaced, or damaged covers, thereby minimizing the risk of accidents and injuries. Moreover, the prevention of unauthorized access is addressed through the implementation of a sophisticated monitoring system that triggers immediate alerts to authorities in the event of suspicious activities, mitigating the risks associated with theft and unauthorized entry. Infrastructure maintenance is another core focus, with the continuous monitoring of manhole covers enabling proactive maintenance measures to minimize the risk of extensive damage and ensure the longevity of the utility network.

The project's technological foundation lies in the integration of advanced sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices, providing real-time data

on the status of manhole covers. This data is then analyzed using machine learning algorithms, facilitating the identification of patterns, prediction of potential issues, and optimization of maintenance schedules. The real-time nature of the monitoring system contributes to cost efficiency in infrastructure management by allowing for proactive maintenance and rapid response to issues, reducing the need for emergency repairs and enabling the allocation of resources more effectively.

Implementation of the Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is envisioned as a collaborative effort involving city authorities, utility companies, and technology partners. The installation of cutting-edge sensors on manhole covers, coupled with a centralized monitoring system, forms the technological backbone of this initiative. A user-friendly interface will be developed, facilitating easy access to real-time data, historical trends, and analytics for city officials and maintenance crews, enabling efficient decision-making. In conclusion, the Manhole Cover Monitoring Project represents a transformative leap towards safer, more resilient urban environments. By embracing technological advancements and adopting proactive maintenance strategies, the initiative aims to elevate the overall quality of life for citizens while safeguarding the critical infrastructure that forms the backbone of our communities. Together, we embark on a journey towards a smarter and safer urban future.

1.1: Problem Statement:

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project responds to a pressing problem in urban infrastructure management that has profound implications for public safety, service continuity, and the overall well-being of communities. In contemporary urban landscapes, manhole covers, essential components of utility networks, face a multitude of challenges, ranging from

theft and unauthorized access to displacement and structural deterioration. These issues not only pose imminent safety risks by creating hazards such as open manholes or damaged covers but also lead to significant disruptions in critical services, including sewage and utility systems. The absence of a robust monitoring system exacerbates these challenges, as the current reactive approach to addressing manhole cover issues often results in delayed responses, escalating repair costs, and potential harm to citizens.

Figure .2: Opened Manhole

Instances of theft or unauthorized entry into manholes not only compromise the integrity of infrastructure but can also lead to criminal activities, underscoring the urgent need for a comprehensive monitoring solution. Additionally, the lack of real-time data on the condition of manhole covers hampers proactive maintenance efforts, contributing to a vicious cycle of increasing risks, escalating costs, and compromised urban infrastructure resilience. The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project emerges as a strategic response to this problem, aiming to introduce an advanced, technology-driven system that not only identifies and addresses existing issues promptly but also establishes a proactive framework for ensuring the sustained integrity of manhole covers, enhancing public safety, and fortifying the foundations of urban infrastructure against evolving challenges.

1.2: Problem Scope:

The scope of the problem addressed by the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is expansive and multifaceted, encompassing critical aspects of urban infrastructure management. The challenges associated with manhole covers within urban environments create a broad problem scope that spans safety concerns, service interruptions, and the long-term resilience of city infrastructure.

Firstly, the safety implications are paramount. Open, displaced, or damaged manhole covers pose immediate risks to public safety, leading to potential accidents, injuries, and even fatalities. The lack of real-time monitoring exacerbates these risks, as timely detection and intervention are crucial to preventing accidents and ensuring the well-being of pedestrians, motorists, and residents.

Secondly, the problem extends to service continuity and the functionality of essential urban utilities. Manhole cover theft, unauthorized access, or structural deterioration can disrupt the seamless operation of sewage and utility lines, leading to service outages and inconveniences for residents. The absence of a proactive monitoring system means that these disruptions are often only addressed reactively, causing delays, increased repair costs, and heightened inconvenience for the community.

Furthermore, the scope of the problem encompasses the financial burden associated with emergency repairs and compromised infrastructure. Reactive maintenance practices, resulting from a lack of real-time data and monitoring capabilities, contribute to escalating costs in infrastructure management. This financial strain affects municipal budgets and diverts resources that could be allocated more efficiently with a proactive and data-driven approach.

The problem scope also extends to the broader resilience and sustainability of urban infrastructure. The challenges with manhole

covers highlight the need for innovative solutions to ensure the longevity and reliability of utility networks. Proactive monitoring and maintenance can play a crucial role in enhancing the overall resilience of urban infrastructure against evolving threats and challenges, contributing to the sustainable development of cities.

In summary, the problem scope of the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project encompasses immediate safety concerns, service interruptions, financial implications, and the long-term resilience of urban infrastructure. By addressing these challenges, the project seeks to create a comprehensive and proactive solution that not only mitigates current issues but also establishes a foundation for the sustainable and resilient management of urban infrastructure in the future.

1.3: Advantages of unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project brings forth a host of advantages that collectively contribute to the enhancement of urban infrastructure management, public safety, and the overall efficiency of city services. The key advantages of implementing this innovative monitoring system are outlined below:

Enhanced Public Safety:

The project significantly improves public safety by promptly identifying and addressing issues with manhole covers. Real-time monitoring ensures that hazards such as open, displaced, or damaged covers are immediately detected, minimizing the risk of accidents, injuries, and potential fatalities.

Prevention of Unauthorized Access:

The monitoring system acts as a robust deterrent against unauthorized access and theft of manhole covers. Swift detection and alerts to authorities enable proactive intervention, preventing criminal activities and safeguarding the integrity of critical infrastructure.

Optimized Infrastructure Maintenance:

By continuously monitoring the condition of manhole covers, the project facilitates proactive maintenance measures. Early detection of wear and tear enables timely repairs and replacements, reducing the need for emergency interventions and optimizing the overall maintenance schedule.

Real-time Data Analysis and Decision-Making:

Leveraging advanced sensor technology and data analytics, the project provides real-time insights into the status of manhole covers. This data-driven approach empowers city officials and maintenance crews with actionable information, facilitating informed decision-making and strategic planning for infrastructure management.

Cost Efficiency in Infrastructure Management:

Proactive maintenance and rapid response to issues contribute to cost efficiency. By preventing major incidents and reducing the need for emergency repairs, the project allows for the allocation of resources more effectively, minimizing operational costs in the long run.

Improved Service Continuity:

The project ensures uninterrupted service delivery by mitigating disruptions caused by manhole cover issues. By addressing challenges such as theft and unauthorized access promptly, the monitoring system helps maintain the seamless operation of sewage and utility lines, preventing service outages and inconveniences for residents.

Long-Term Infrastructure Resilience:

Implementing a proactive monitoring system establishes a foundation for long-term infrastructure resilience. By leveraging real-time data and analytics, the project aids in identifying patterns, predicting potential issues, and developing strategies to enhance the overall

resilience of urban infrastructure against evolving challenges.

Technological Innovation and Smart Cities:

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project positions the city as a technological innovator and contributor to the development of smart cities. Embracing advanced sensor technology and data analytics reflects a commitment to leveraging innovation for the improvement of urban living conditions and infrastructure sustainability.

The advantages of the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project extend beyond immediate problem resolution, impacting public safety, infrastructure efficiency, and the city's overall readiness to meet the demands of a dynamic urban environment. Through the integration of advanced monitoring technologies, the project sets the stage for a safer, more resilient, and technologically advanced urban landscape.

1.4 Proposed System

The proposed system for the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is a comprehensive and technologically advanced solution designed to address the challenges associated with manhole covers in urban environments. This system incorporates a combination of cutting-edge sensor technologies, real-time data analytics, and a centralized monitoring platform to ensure the continuous and proactive oversight of manhole covers. The key components of the proposed system include:

Advanced Sensors and IoT Devices:

High-tech sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices will be strategically installed on each manhole cover to monitor various parameters, including position, temperature, and structural integrity. These sensors will provide real-time data on the status of the manhole covers, enabling immediate detection of any abnormalities.

Wireless Communication Infrastructure:

A robust wireless communication infrastructure will be implemented to facilitate seamless connectivity between the sensors on manhole covers and the centralized monitoring platform. This ensures the timely transmission of data, allowing for swift response to emerging issues.

Centralized Monitoring Platform:

The heart of the system is a centralized monitoring platform that aggregates and analyzes data from all sensors in real-time. This platform will employ advanced data analytics and machine learning algorithms to identify patterns, predict potential issues, and generate actionable insights for infrastructure management.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

1.5.1: Aim

The aim of the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is to fundamentally transform urban infrastructure management by implementing an innovative and proactive monitoring system specifically designed for manhole covers. This project aims to achieve several key objectives, including enhancing public safety by swiftly identifying and addressing issues related to manhole covers, such as open, displaced, or damaged covers. The primary focus is on real-time monitoring to promptly detect potential safety hazards and minimize the risks of accidents, injuries, and fatalities.

Additionally, the project seeks to act as a robust deterrent against unauthorized access and theft of manhole covers by employing advanced detection mechanisms and immediate alerts to authorities. This proactive approach not only safeguards critical infrastructure but also contributes to preventing criminal activities associated with unauthorized entry and theft.

Optimizing infrastructure maintenance is a central goal of the project, with continuous monitoring of manhole covers facilitating early detection of wear and tear. This proactive

approach is intended to enable timely repairs and replacements, reducing the need for emergency interventions and optimizing the overall maintenance schedule.

Through the integration of advanced sensor technology and data analytics, the project aims to provide real-time insights into the status of manhole covers. This empowers city officials and maintenance crews with actionable information for informed decision-making and strategic planning in infrastructure management. Cost efficiency in infrastructure management is another significant aim, achieved through proactive maintenance practices that mitigate major incidents and minimize the need for emergency repairs. This approach allows for the more effective allocation of resources.

Ensuring uninterrupted service delivery and improving service continuity are integral components of the project. By maintaining the seamless operation of sewage and utility lines, the project aims to prevent service outages and inconveniences for residents.

Moreover, the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project seeks to contribute to the long-term resilience of urban infrastructure by establishing a foundation for resilience through the use of real-time data and analytics.

Finally, the project aims to position the city as a technological innovator by embracing advanced sensor technology and data analytics. This commitment underscores the city's dedication to leveraging technological innovation for the betterment of urban living conditions and the sustainability of critical infrastructure.

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project aims to create a safer, more efficient, and technologically advanced urban environment. It addresses immediate challenges associated with manhole covers while laying the groundwork for proactive and sustainable infrastructure management.

1.5.2 Objectives

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project is designed with a set of specific and interrelated objectives, each contributing to the overarching aim of transforming urban infrastructure management. The key objectives of the project include:

Enhancing Public Safety:

- Promptly identify and address issues with manhole covers to minimize the risk of accidents, injuries, and fatalities.
- Implement real-time monitoring to detect hazards such as open, displaced, or damaged covers.

Preventing Unauthorized Access and Theft:

- Act as a robust deterrent against unauthorized access and theft of manhole covers.
- Employ advanced detection mechanisms and immediate alerts to authorities for swift intervention.

Optimizing Infrastructure Maintenance:

- Continuously monitor the condition of manhole covers to enable proactive maintenance.
- Early detection of wear and tear for timely repairs and replacements, reducing the need for emergency interventions.

Real-time Data Analysis and Decision-Making:

- Utilize advanced sensor technology and data analytics to provide real-time insights into the status of manhole covers.
- Empower city officials and maintenance crews with actionable information for informed decision-making and strategic planning.

Cost Efficiency in Infrastructure Management:

- Implement proactive maintenance practices to mitigate major incidents

and minimize the need for emergency repairs.

- Optimize resource allocation for more effective and cost-efficient infrastructure management.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature survey for the Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring Project extensively explores current research, technologies, and methodologies related to the monitoring and management of manhole covers, urban infrastructure, and the integration of sensor technologies within smart city initiatives. With the primary goal of providing insights into the contemporary state of knowledge, identifying existing gaps, and laying the groundwork for innovative contributions, the survey delves into several key aspects.

Highlighting the significance of proactive maintenance and real-time monitoring in urban infrastructure management, the literature underscores the challenges associated with aging infrastructure and advocates for the prompt deployment of advanced technologies. A detailed examination of manhole cover monitoring technologies reveals a growing interest in sensor-based solutions, encompassing accelerometers, pressure sensors, and temperature sensors. Studies explore the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and wireless communication for comprehensive monitoring, showcasing a diverse array of approaches.

The literature emphasizes the critical connection between public safety and urban infrastructure resilience, particularly focusing on the repercussions of open or displaced manhole covers on safety, traffic flow, and emergency response. Sensor technologies are identified as pivotal in enhancing safety and resilience, acting as key enablers in addressing these challenges.

A significant portion of the literature survey is dedicated to preventing unauthorized access and

theft of manhole covers, recognizing the security implications of such incidents. Discussions encompass anti-theft mechanisms, smart locks, and real-time alerts, all aimed at preserving the integrity of utility networks and preventing criminal activities.

The application of data analytics in infrastructure management emerges as a critical theme, with a focus on the role of machine learning algorithms in predicting issues, optimizing maintenance schedules, and improving decision-making processes. Economic benefits associated with proactive maintenance are explored, with case studies illustrating how cities can achieve cost savings and allocate resources more effectively.

The literature also delves into the broader context of smart city initiatives, highlighting the role of sensor technologies in various applications, including infrastructure monitoring. The interconnectedness of urban systems is emphasized, showcasing the potential for integrating manhole cover monitoring into comprehensive smart city frameworks.

Addressing concerns related to privacy and data security in sensor-based infrastructure monitoring, the literature explores encryption protocols, secure data transmission, and compliance with data protection regulations. These considerations aim to mitigate privacy issues and ensure the integrity of collected data.

In conclusion, the literature survey provides a holistic understanding of the current state of research and technology pertaining to manhole cover monitoring, urban infrastructure management, and smart city initiatives.

III. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The Unveiling Manhole Cover Monitoring project follows a meticulous methodology to comprehensively address the monitoring and management of manhole covers within urban infrastructure. Initially, an extensive literature review is conducted to gain insights into existing

research, technologies, and methodologies related to the project's scope, focusing on manhole cover monitoring, urban infrastructure management, and sensor integration in smart cities. This literature review serves as the foundation for identifying gaps and challenges in the field. The project's objectives are then clearly defined, encompassing aims such as enhancing public safety, improving infrastructure resilience, preventing unauthorized access, and optimizing maintenance processes.

Figure .3: Block diagram

The selection of appropriate sensors is a crucial step, guided by insights from the literature review. Various sensor types, including accelerometers, pressure sensors, and temperature sensors, are considered for their effectiveness in real-time anomaly detection. The methodology emphasizes the integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices to facilitate comprehensive monitoring and reliable data transmission.

Data collection involves deploying selected sensors on manhole covers in designated monitoring areas. The objective is to collect data on parameters such as movement, pressure changes, and temperature fluctuations, ensuring a continuous and reliable data stream for effective monitoring. A real-time monitoring system is developed, incorporating algorithms to detect anomalies promptly and trigger immediate alerts for timely response.

Security measures are integrated into the system to prevent unauthorized access, encompassing encryption protocols, secure data transmission,

and authentication mechanisms. Anti-theft mechanisms, such as smart locks and tamper detection systems, are employed to safeguard against manhole cover theft. The methodology also emphasizes the application of data analytics, including machine learning algorithms, to analyze collected data, predict potential issues, optimize maintenance schedules, and enhance decision-making processes for infrastructure management.

Privacy concerns related to sensor-based infrastructure monitoring are addressed by ensuring compliance with data protection regulations and implementing measures to protect individuals' privacy while maintaining the utility of collected data. Thorough testing and validation are conducted in real-world conditions to verify the accuracy of sensor data, the effectiveness of anomaly detection, and the responsiveness of the real-time monitoring system.

Upon successful testing, the monitoring system is deployed in selected urban areas in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, such as local authorities and utility companies. The methodology establishes a continuous improvement framework, monitoring system performance over time, gathering user feedback, and implementing updates or enhancements to address evolving needs and challenges. Overall, this methodology ensures a comprehensive, technologically advanced, and practically effective approach to unveiling manhole cover monitoring within the context of urban infrastructure management.

IV. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

4.1 NodeMCU (ESP8266)

The NodeMCU ESP8266 is a powerful and versatile platform designed for Internet of Things (IoT) development. The ESP8266 is a cost-effective Wi-Fi microchip known for its capability to enable wireless communication in IoT applications. NodeMCU, on the other hand,

is an open-source firmware and development kit that simplifies the process of prototyping and programming the ESP8266. With built-in Wi-Fi connectivity, the NodeMCU ESP8266 allows devices to connect to the internet wirelessly, making it suitable for a wide range of IoT projects. One notable feature is its support for the Lua scripting language, providing a high-level programming environment for developers. Additionally, it is compatible with the Arduino IDE, allowing those familiar with Arduino to use the NodeMCU platform. Equipped with General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) pins, the ESP8266 facilitates interfacing with various electronic components, making it ideal for applications such as home automation and sensor networks. The NodeMCU ESP8266 has garnered significant community support, resulting in an extensive collection of libraries and documentation, making it a popular choice for rapid IoT prototyping and development.

Figure.4: NodeMCU 2D View

Figure.5: NodeMCU Parts

The NodeMCU ESP8266 development board typically has GPIO (General Purpose

Input/Output) pins that can be used for various purposes, including interfacing with sensors, actuators, and other electronic components. Below is a common pinout configuration for the NodeMCU development board

Figure .6: NodeMCU ESP8266 Pinout

4.2: Float Sensor

Float switches are used in various industrial processes for point-level detection which means these switches give an indication that a liquid level is normally open or normally closed at a specific level. These switches work for detecting foaming, dielectric, conductivity, pressure, temperature, vacuum, vapors, condensation, boiling effects, vibrations, and bubble formation. So these switches are appropriate for almost all types of liquids. This switching operation is contact-free and doesn't need a voltage supply. So due to the simple functional principle of this switch, it can be used in a wide range of applications ranging from general industrial applications to process plants & shipbuilding industry. This article discusses an overview of a float switch – working with applications.

What is a Float Switch?

A float switch definition is: It is a type of contact liquid level sensor which uses a float to operate a switch within a tank. This switch is also known as a level sensor. These switches play a key role in controlling other devices like pumps & alarms when a level of liquid increases or drops to a particular point. The float switch symbol is shown below. These switches range from small sizes to large sizes. Float switches come in two different styles:

magnetic(Electromagnetic) and Mechanical float type.

Figure .7: Switch Symbols

Construction of Float Switch:

The construction of this electromagnetic switch can be done with a stem, reed switch, and permanent magnet.

Figure.8: Float sensor Construction

Float Switch Working Principle

The working of a float switch is based on the principle of buoyancy i.e., when there is no liquid in contact with the float, it floats on top of the liquid surface and triggers an alarm signal, when there is a sufficient amount of liquid in contact with float, it submerges itself into liquid and stops alarming. The principle of operation is the same for both the style of float switches but works depending on their construction of it. Let's see how both work.

Figure .9 : Float Sensor Working

4.3 Relay Module:

Figure .10: Relay Module

4.4 LED Strip Lights

A 12V power supply for LED strip lights, as the name suggests, is a device that converts the AC voltage from your electrical outlet into a steady and regulated 12V DC output. LED strip lights operate on low voltage DC power, making a 12V power supply an essential component to provide the necessary power for illuminating the LED strips.

The reliability of your power supply is crucial for maintaining the longevity and performance of your LED strip lights. A high-quality power supply ensures a stable and consistent power output, which is vital for the proper functioning of LED strip lights. Fluctuations in voltage or current can lead to flickering lights, reduced brightness, or even damage to the LEDs themselves. Therefore, investing in a reliable power supply is paramount to avoid any potential issues and maximize the lifespan of your LED strip lights.

Choosing the Right Power Supply for Your LED Strip Lights

When it comes to choosing the right power supply for your LED strip lights, several factors need to be taken into consideration.

Figure 11 : 12V LED Strip Lights

4.5 IR Sensor

IR sensor is an electronic device, that emits the light in order to sense some object of the surroundings. An IR sensor can measure the heat of an object as well as detects the motion. Usually, in the infrared spectrum, all the objects radiate some form of thermal radiation. These types of radiations are invisible to our eyes, but infrared sensor can detect these radiations.

The emitter is simply an IR LED (Light Emitting Diode) and the detector is simply an IR photodiode . Photodiode is sensitive to IR light of the same wavelength which is emitted by the IR LED. When IR light falls on the photodiode, the resistances and the output voltages will change in proportion to the magnitude of the IR light received.

Figure .12 : IR Sensor

There are five basic elements used in a typical infrared detection system: an infrared source, a transmission medium, optical component, infrared detectors or receivers and signal processing. Infrared lasers and Infrared LED's of specific wavelength used as infrared sources. The three main types of media used for infrared transmission are vacuum, atmosphere and

optical fibers. Optical components are used to focus the infrared radiation or to limit the spectral response.

V. CONCLUSION

The future vision of a smart city is to have better and cleaner facilities for the general public. Intelligent subterranean infrastructure is an essential component that should be taken into account while building a rational city. System monitoring is essential to maintaining the town's health and cleanliness. Due to the incompetence of manual monitoring, drainage issues are handled slowly and take longer to resolve.

The technology uses a wireless sensor network made up of sensor nodes to lessen these problems. The suggested system is an IoT-based real-time system that is low maintenance, low cost, and sends an email alert to the management station if any manhole exceeds its threshold values. In addition to helping the public, this method lowers the danger of mortality for manual scavengers who clean the subterranean drainage system.

Through the Internet of Things, a sensor unit may automatically detect and update the current values of physical characteristics such as temperature, humidity, water level and flow, obstructions, and whether a manhole lid is open or closed. This adds intelligence and automation to the system.

In developing nations, the deployment of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) facilitates the establishment of Smart Cities. The design of environmental monitoring systems, which support the monitoring of volcanic activity, flood detectors, and other systems, may also benefit from the usage of this WSN. With minor implementation adjustments, this project is often used to monitor and manage systems in sectors related to agricultural or other environmental concerns. The infrastructure of smart cities may change in the future to allow for intelligent administration and communication of street

lighting, active lanes, transit apps, traffic signals, and other features. The integration of smart gadgets with civic infrastructure may greatly simplify city living.

Drainage water is also often monitored, regulated, and used to irrigate plants, clean restrooms, and other things thanks to PLC controllers and SCADA systems. Drainage water treatment is a common usage for these PLC and SCADA systems. PLC primarily regulates the sewage treatment plant's operation, and SCADA, which may be a link-attached terminal unit that oversees and manages the whole region.

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